

NEW METHODS FOR DETECTING AND TREATMENT OF INFERTILITY OF TUBE-PERITONEAL GENESIS

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ABSTRACT

Tubal-perineal infertility is characterized by anatomical and functional disorders of the fallopian tubes with the development of adhesions in the pelvic cavity, which develops in 65% of cases due to a chronic inflammatory process in the female genital organs [1,2]. The paper presents an analysis of the examination of women to identify an effective method for diagnosing and treating infertility of tubal-perineal origin. Measures were taken for the early rehabilitation of tubal infertility and their effectiveness was studied.

Relevance. One of the main health problems of motherhood and childhood is an increase in the frequency of female infertility [1,2,3]. Now the frequency of infertile marriages in Uzbekistan is about 15%, it tends to increase. Tubal infertility occurs in 30-74% of cases, and peritoneal infertility 34% of the total number of all infertility. As a result, effective diagnosis of the causes of tubal-peritoneal infertility is of particular importance in the diagnosis and treatment of infertility in general.

Purpose of the study. To reveal effective methods of diagnostics and treatment of tubal-peritoneal infertility.

Materials and methods of research. 60 women with secondary infertility were examined in the first clinic of the Samarkand Medical University, admitted from 2019 to 2021. All patients underwent a general clinical examination, studied the

duration and nature of the course of the tubal-peritoneal infertility factor, previous conservative treatment and its duration, laboratory research methods included bacteriological studies, taking vaginal smears for purity, smears from the cervical canal for testing for chlamydial, ureaplasma and mycoplasma infection, herpes simplex virus (HSV), cytomegalovirus (CMV) by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). In order to exclude the endocrine cause of infertility, hormonal studies were performed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay to determine hormones in blood plasma (PRL, LH, FSH, testosterone, progesterone, estradiol).

To solve the tasks set, special studies were carried out: to assess the degree of patency of the fallopian tubes and their functional state, the method of kymopertubation was used on days 19-21 of the menstrual cycle.

30 minutes before the procedure, the patient was injected intramuscularly with 5.0 ml of baralgin, which reduced the possibility of spasm of the fallopian tube sphincter.

In addition, all patients underwent hysterosalpingography according to the generally accepted method using water-soluble contrasts (urographin). Dynamic hysteroscopy and hydrotubation were also performed according to the generally accepted method.

As a treatment, laparoscopy was performed with various options for conservative plastic surgery of the fallopian tubes, peritubar and periovarian space, before which anti-inflammatory therapy was performed, taking into account the identified infectious agent and sensitivity. During the operation, endoscopic chromosalpingoscopy was performed and the site of fallopian tube occlusion was determined. The operation ended with the creation of a hydroperitoneum with a solution of polyglucin. After that, the patients were divided into 2 groups: the 1st group of patients with traditional treatment (control group) and the second - the main group with complex rehabilitation treatment according to the method developed by us.

The first group included 25 patients who underwent traditional drug and physiotherapy treatment in the pre- and postoperative periods, and the second group included 25 patients (main group) who underwent hydrotubation in the early (from 2-3 days) postoperative period, physiotherapy treatment according to the developed by us methodology.

Our proposed complex for early rehabilitation of patients with tubal

infertility after laparoscopic surgery consists of the following components:

- Anti-inflammatory therapy in the preoperative period.
- Carrying out a laparoscopic operation to restore the patency of the fallopian tubes, chromosalpingography and hydroperitoneum with a solution of polyglucin (200 ml).
- Antibiotic prophylaxis in the postoperative period by intravenous administration of a daily dose of antibiotic and metronidazole for 5-7 days.
- Artificial hydroperitoneum with a solution of polyglucin (200 ml) on the 2nd-3rd day of the postoperative period.
- Hydrotubation with a solution of polyglucin on days 3, 4 and 5 of the postoperative period.
- Appointment of quantum therapy from the first day of the postoperative period according to the scheme developed by us.
- Drugs that improve microcirculation and blood rheology (trental, reopoliglyukin, chimes).
- Carrying out further rehabilitation until the next menstruation, as in the comparison group, but with the use of quantum therapy.

Results: All women had a history of chronic inflammatory diseases of the genital organs, 33 (66%) patients had complications in a previous pregnancy, which led to delivery by operation, Caesarean section. According to ultrasound, chronic endometritis was diagnosed in 15 (30%), foreign objects (ligatures) were found in the uterine cavity in 7 (14%), endometrial polyps in 5 (10%) and in 2 cases - subserous uterine myoma (4%) . Patients with inflammatory diseases were prescribed anti-inflammatory

therapy before cymopertubation. After that, all patients underwent cymopertubation on the 19-21st day of the menstrual cycle. Half an hour before this procedure, the patients were injected intramuscularly with 5.0 ml of baralgin to reduce the possible development of spasm of the sphincter of the fallopian tubes. According to the results of the study, in 6 (12%) women the patency of the tubes was difficult, in 12 (24%) the tubes were passable, but the peristalsis was weak or absent. In 32 (64%) women, the tubes were passable and peristalsis was well expressed.

The study of hysterosalpingography was carried out on the 19-21st day of the menstrual cycle and half an hour before the procedure, the patients were injected with 5.0 ml of baralgin or antispasmodics in order to reduce the possible spasm of the fallopian tube sphincter, a water-soluble contrast - urographin was used as a dye. As a result, 10 (20%) patients had obstruction of the fallopian tubes, 4 (8%) patients had an uneven contour of the fallopian tube orifice area, and a defect in the filling of the uterine cavity in 5 (10%) cases.

Hysteroscopy was performed after preparatory treatment. Hysteroscopic examination of women diagnosed the following conditions: chronic endometritis in 17 (34%), ligature in the uterine cavity - in 11 (22%), endometrial polyps in 5 women (10%), polyps in the mouth of the fallopian tube in 2 (4%), synechia - in 4 (8%) and adhesions in the uterine cavity and fallopian tubes in 26 (52%) patients. It is worth noting that in patients with a scar on the uterus, a combination of adhesive processes in the uterine cavity and / or fallopian tubes with ligatures in the uterine cavity was observed.

Laparoscopy revealed 2 (4%) cases of subserous fibroids, which were removed, endoscopic chromosalpingoscopy was performed and obstruction of the fallopian tubes was detected in 30 (60%) patients. After laparoscopy, the patients were under control in the hospital for up to 7 days, after which the control continued for a year on an outpatient basis.

All patients a month after discharge from the hospital underwent a course of physiotherapy from 12-14 days of the menstrual cycle for 10-14 days, with the use of physiotherapy and quantum therapy in the main group.

After the treatment in the control group, fertility was restored within 6 months in 10 out of 25 patients, and in the second group, 9 out of 25 spontaneous pregnancies were observed after 3 months, after 6 months, uterine pregnancy was confirmed in 8 patients. During treatment, if necessary, ovarian stimulation was performed 3 months after surgery.

Conclusion. Based on the results, it can be said that the diagnosis of secondary infertility includes various methods with their own advantages and disadvantages, but the best method for diagnosing secondary infertility, and especially tubal-peritoneal genesis, is endosurgical methods - hysteroscopy and laparoscopy. Their reliability and effectiveness are undeniable, since they can be used not only for diagnosis, but also for the simultaneous treatment of various pathologies.

With early rehabilitation of patients after laparoscopy and hysteroscopy, fertility restoration takes half the time in 36% of cases, and the efficiency is 68%, in contrast to the first group in which the fertility restoration rate was 36% within 6 months after surgery.

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